

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TEACHING OF PATRIOTISM IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING HISTORY IN MODERN TIMES

Bayramova U.,

Baku State University branch of Kazakh, phd student
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6719-3546

Süleymanov M.

Baku State University branch of Kazakh, phd student
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7544-3437

Abstract

All the subjects taught at the school not only provide students with scientific knowledge, but also serve to grow the young generation in national and moral qualities, especially in the spirit of patriotism. In this regard, history has a greater responsibility. More precisely, education of citizens useful to society and with a broad outlook is the direct duty of the history subject and history teachers. All the subjects taught in the school not only provide scientific knowledge to the students, but also serve to grow the young generation in national and moral qualities, especially in the spirit of patriotism. In this regard, history has a greater responsibility.

Key words: society, citizen, responsibility, teaching, youth.

Introduction

The level of development of society is related to education, which reflects the essence of socio-economic processes. In all civilized countries, giving importance to education as the basis of development, its acceptance as a superior activity field of special strategic importance for the society and the state is related to the role played by education in the life of the society, its being the beginning of all kinds of development and progress.

Today, the development of our independent republic depends, first of all, on the correct organization of the education and training of the growing generation, and the preparation for citizenship. The role of family and society are great in the development of children as citizens. Children receive their first education as a person, a citizen in the family, including in society. Here they have moral and spiritual qualities, physical strength, rules of conduct, etc. they gain such qualities. Undoubtedly, the main goal of education is to train a perfect personality and citizen. Educating a citizen means educating a person who works for the development of the state to which he belongs, looks after its interests, and is responsible for its security.

Main part

A person is born as an individual, acts as a citizen and undergoes civil training in the process of education and labor. A real citizen means a person who directly serves the country and the state with his necessary activities and has great moral qualities. Experience shows that the correct establishment of citizenship education in the family depends very much on the level of the citizenship position of the parents themselves. Citizenship education means acquiring high moral and spiritual qualities of children and bringing them up as individuals. [5] In other words, children should know the history, geography, culture, national traditions of their homeland, love the homeland, be responsible, honest, and fighters. In order to evaluate the moral education of children, it is very important to instill in them human qualities such as distinguishing good from evil, respecting truth, justice, elders, and family members. The

mentioned reflects the essence of citizenship education. As the Republic of Azerbaijan develops, special attention is paid to the education of patriotism, including military-patriotic education of the growing generation. Of course, the people of Azerbaijan do not want war. Our people have supported peace and tranquility throughout history. In historical events, the brave sons of our nation only stood guard and defended our homeland.

Education in the military-patriotic spirit cannot be limited to ordinary words and advice. In order to achieve success in this field, schools must, first of all, plan their work correctly and determine the work they will do during the year. At this time, the connection between the measures, their complementarity should be taken into account, and the organization of the work should be justified. Our great leader, the architect and founder of our independent Azerbaijan, Heydar Aliyev, attaches special importance to patriotic education and the growth of children and youth in a patriotic spirit, and he repeatedly recommended this in his speeches.

The feeling of love for the motherland should be manifested in the commitment of young people to the state language, national music, folklore, religious values, historical traditions, and the fact that they are ready to protect the integrity of the country's territory through practical work. In order to work for the progress of the motherland, it is also an important factor that young people have a certain art, profession, and actively participate in state building. It is important for the young generation to acquire education, have a broad outlook, and love work. To protect the material and spiritual wealth of the motherland, to achieve the rise of its economic power, to always be able to fight against the riots, provocations and natural disasters that may occur comes from the love of the motherland. [6] It is possible to better inculcate military-patriotic education in young people when students studying in X-XI grades of secondary school and students-young people studying in higher school are given military-related knowledge while teaching separate subjects and specialized courses.

During the time of the Soviet Union, in the existing textbooks, teaching aids and methodical literature, information instilling military-patriotic feelings and military-related knowledge were given little space. In fact, this was done consciously so that young people would be deprived of patriotism and national feelings. The feeling of citizenship is a high manifestation of love for the country. Patriotism, which is one of the highest human feelings, stems from love for the village, land, and country where everyone is born and raised. But patriotism is not only loving the country. Patriotism is also working for the sake of the motherland, being ready to protect the motherland at all times, showing heroism and sacrifices in its path, and having a share in every success of the motherland and the people. Although this feeling is innate in a person, like all other feelings, it needs education and is strengthened through education. [7] Since patriotism is one of the most important qualities characterizing a person, its instillation in the growing generation, upbringing of children, teenagers and young people in the spirit of patriotism has always been one of the most important directions of education.

National leader Heydar Aliyev has always prioritized citizenship education in his political course, and emphasized the importance of patriotic education in all his speeches. [4] As a result of his successful political course, a real civil society and patriotic sons were formed. As a successful result of this policy, President Ilham Aliyev and the brave Azerbaijani army, patriotic sons of Azerbaijan demonstrated true patriotism to the world in the 44-day Second Karabakh War.

Conclusion

In modern times, the task of educating active citizens is realized precisely as a result of systematic and consistent patriotism education. It is known that the foundation of patriotism education is laid in primary classes, as in all fields and directions of education and training, and it is further developed in the subsequent stages of education. In this sense, primary school teachers have a great responsibility in the patriotism education of the growing generation. They should try to instill love for the motherland in the hearts of young children entering school from the very first days, and turn this love into a strong feeling of patriotism.

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